

This archive contains input data files and 3d data files from the simulations of the Space Weather Modeling Framework (SWMF).

In the swmf-input folder,

- The data provided in GaussCoeff.txt can be used to obtain the paleomagnetic intrinsic magnetic field during the inversion period through the spherical harmonic function.
- The data provided in IMF_ideal.dat is used as the upstream solar wind input condition of SWMF.

The mgt-3d-simu folder contains 3d magnetospheric simulation data at different times during the geomagnetic reversal.

These simulations were performed for and used in the paper “Simulating the Solar Wind-Magnetosphere Interaction During the Matuyama-Brunhes Paleomagnetic Reversal” Gong, F., Yu, Y., Cao, J., Wei, Y., Gao, J., Li, H., Zhang, B., submitted to Geophysical Research Letters, 2021.